

Quantum Space-time Relation for both Massive Particles and Photons from Relativity Part 2

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In Part I, we noted that although $E=pc$ may be related to $x=ct$ for a photon, leading to the speculative result: $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ ((1)), these relations only hold for a photon. We thus proposed: $E x - pc ct = 0$ ((2)) which holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass and argued that $\text{constant}/E = \Delta t$ and $\text{constant}/p = \Delta x$.

Here we ask: What is the physical underlying scenario behind such statements? Certainly E and p are related to Newtonian concepts and there is no gradation of x or t linked to E or p there. We suggest that for ((1)) to make sense it must be verified experimentally (which has been done through 2-slit interference etc), but also, that there must be a physical reason which is somehow linked to special relativity because the relation ((2)) is obtained directly from this theory.

We suggest that special relativity suggests the presence of a velocity parameter b which is the same in all reference frames. ($b=c$) We have argued in previous notes that a moving frame ($-v$) essentially changes momentum p (and E) and not necessarily all speeds. If $b=c$ is the same in all frames (and an upper bound speed), we suggest that it is a property of space. In fact, we link it to ϵ_0 , electrical permittivity and μ_0 , magnetic permittivity. This, we argue, suggests some kind of period motion to create such a speed (like a wave in a physical medium). There is no physical medium, however, as we show from the electromagnetic equations. We argue that given that various p_i , E_i are linked with the same c , the periodicity must distinguish various p , E_i . Thus, there is an actual physical periodicity associated with a particular momentum p_i for a photon. p is not simply a measure of impulse. This is born out in 2-slit experiments. This wave-like periodicity follows for c being a property of space (ϵ_0 , μ_0), but momentum is a general concept and it is the momentum which measures the length of the periodicity.

If one wishes momentum to be a universal idea (as in ((2))), then one should suggest that there exists an actual fluctuation/periodicity associated for p for a particle with rest mass as well. This exists as shown through 2-slit experiments. Thus, ((1)) seems to hold because it is a description of a physical fluctuation/periodicity which is associated with E and p , something that is not seen in Newtonian mechanics, but seems to follow from special relativity. In other words, E and p are more complicated than they seem in Newtonian mechanics.

Ex - pcct = 0

The relation, $E x - pcct = 0$ ((2)), obtained in Part 1, from special relativity, is unusual in that it links x, t with E, p and holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass. One may argue that E and p are linked to v for a particle with rest mass and one is really only introducing $x=vt$. Although this is true, ((2)) applies to both a particle with rest mass and a photon which have different E, p , speed relations. Furthermore, E and p for a particle with rest mass are obtained from a Lorentz transformation which focuses on how interaction variables are viewed from a frame moving with $-v$.

We argued in Part 1, that one may try to make ((2)) pertain entirely to space and this leads to:

$$\Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \text{constant}/E \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is not entirely satisfying, however, because it is not associated with physical properties which cause E, p to be linked with gradations and one may still try to argue that E and p are being used to substitute v or c.

As a result, we try to provide physical reasons for ((1)).

Upper Bound c in Lorentz Transformations

A Lorentz transformation really applies to p and E, interaction variables, but may also be used mathematically to transform:

$$(x, bt) \quad ((3))$$

Here b is a constant with units of velocity which is the same in all frames. If this is a physical velocity, then it is not changed as seen in a moving frame. We argue that that is fine as long as it is not linked with momentum (i.e. interaction). V for a particle with rest mass is linked with momentum, but c is not because $E=pc$. Various E,p pairs have the same c. Thus, b is an upper bound speed which may be set to c because the Lorentz transformation applies to:

$$M_0 \text{ at rest at } x=0, t \rightarrow x', t' \text{ with } x'/t'=v \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{or}$$

$$x/t=c \rightarrow x'/t' = c \text{ which yields } b=c \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{photon}$$

If c is really a speed which does not depend on a reference frame, then it seems like a property of space. We argue that it is linked to ϵ_0 , electrical permittivity and μ_0 , magnetic permittivity:

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad ((5))$$

One may obtain ((5)) by creating wave equations for the electric and magnetic fields using Maxwell's electromagnetic equations with no sources. In such a case, one has periodic electric and magnetic fields perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion of the photon. At this point, there is no notion of momentum. The electric and magnetic fields almost seem to create the medium through which the periodic disturbance moves. One may argue that this description follows from Maxwell's equations and not from special relativity.

We argue that given $E=pc$ from special relativity, c is frame independent and seems to be a property of space. It almost seems analogous to the speed of a wave in a medium, but there is no medium here. Nevertheless, one may postulate some kind of periodic motion in space which establishes c, but also allows for different E,p pairs to be distinguished physically through $E=pc$. In other words, p (momentum) is linked with a periodic length because there is periodic motion of the photon with c. p is not simply the creator of impulse as in Newtonian mechanics. This suggestion follows even without knowledge of Maxwell's equations.

Thus, special relativity leads to a c speed which is the same in all frames and seems to be related to properties of space. This leads to the notion of periodic motion, but the period in space and time must distinguish p and E because one has many pairs for $E=pc$.

These arguments apply to a photon and show that momentum is really associated with fluctuating/periodic motion which leads to unusual force interactions because the electric field and magnetic fields interact. One might argue that there is justification for interactions with both slits of a two slit apparatus with spacing of about \hbar/p . The momentum p seems to be linked with fluctuating or periodic motion and is not simply an arrow in the direction of motion.

If one argues that all momenta behave in the same manner, then this idea must also apply to a particle with rest mass. We note that ((2)) holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass and one may make the $\Delta x, \Delta t$ arguments ((1)) for the photon, so it seems natural that the same arguments should apply to a particle with rest mass because ((2)) applies to both. If there were two different kinds of momenta (a non-fluctuating, non-periodic one and a fluctuating-periodic one), there should be two separate equations instead of ((2)), we argue. Thus, we suggest that the $\Delta x, \Delta t$ ((1)) arguments linked to the special relativistic equation ((2)) are really statements that there exists a kind of physical fluctuation/periodicity linked with p, E . In the case of p , one sees this manifested in a 2-slit experiment. This is a feature which goes beyond Newtonian mechanics and so we associate this kind of physical periodicity-fluctuation with free particle quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I, we argued that the special relativistic equation ((2)): $E^2 - pc^2 = 0$ applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass and that if one wishes to interpret this equation strictly in terms of space-time, it seems that: $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$.

This, however, is a rather dramatic statement and so we try to provide some possible physical evidence which follows from special relativity. We argue that special relativity, derived from space time arguments, leads to the introduction of a parameter b with speed units. " B " is the same in all frames. One may show that $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum. We suggest that this means that c is a property of space, i.e of ϵ_0, μ_0 , electrical and magnetic permittivities. We argue that in order for such a speed to be created in space, it must act somewhat like a wave, but without a medium. (Physically, this is seen from Maxwell's equations in which periodic electric and magnetic fields "create" in a sense the medium in which the photon periodically moves.) With or without Maxwell's equation, the periodicity is needed to distinguish p, E pairs because $E=pc$. Thus, p is not simply an impulse hit number, but is associated with spatial periodicity or fluctuations and E , with time ones. We suggest that given that equation ((2)) applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass, this physical periodicity-fluctuation feature must also exist for a particle with rest mass. This leads to non-Newtonian behaviour which we argue is the feature of free particle quantum mechanics. In other words, E and p are physically associated with fluctuations/periodicity in time/space.